

UDDER THERMOGRAPHY IN DAIRY EWES

1 **The use of infrared thermography to detect mastitis in dairy ewes.** *By Castro-Costa et al.*

2 A flock of Manchega and Lacaune dairy ewes were used to assess the ability of an
3 infrared camera for detecting clinical and subclinical mastitis, naturally occurring or induced
4 by *E. coli* endotoxin infusion, at early- (n = 83) or at late-lactation (n = 9), respectively. Udder
5 temperature varied by breed and milking, but we were unable to discriminate between
6 healthy, infected or infused *E. coli* udders. Udder skin and ambient temperature correlated.
7 Despite the camera sensitivity, factors other than intramammary infections can change udder
8 temperature and confound the detection **signs**.

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15 **Thermographic variation of the udder of dairy ewes in early-lactation and**
16 **following an *E. coli* endotoxin intramammary challenge in late-lactation**

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31 ABSTRACT

32 A total of 83 lactating dairy ewes (Manchega, n = 48; Lacaune, n = 35) were used in 2
33 consecutive experiments for assessing the ability of infrared thermography (IRT) to detect
34 intramammary infections (IMI) by measuring udder skin temperatures (UST). In Exp. 1, ewes
35 were milked twice-daily and IRT pictures of the udder taken before and after milking at 46
36 and 56 DIM. Milk yield was 1.46 ± 0.04 L/d, on average. Detection of IMI was done using
37 standard bacterial culture by udder half at 15, 34 and 64 DIM. Twenty-two ewes were
38 classified as having IMI in at least one udder half, the others being healthy (142 healthy and
39 24 IMI halves, respectively). Four IMI halves had clinical mastitis. No UST differences were
40 detected by IMI and udder side, being $32.94 \pm 0.04^\circ\text{C}$, on average. Nevertheless, differences
41 in UST were detected by breed (Manchega – Lacaune = $0.35 \pm 0.08^\circ\text{C}$), milking process
42 moment (before – after = $0.13 \pm 0.11^\circ\text{C}$) and milking schedule (a.m. – p.m. = $0.79 \pm 0.07^\circ\text{C}$).
43 The UST increased linearly with ambient temperature ($r = 0.88$). In Exp. 2, the UST response
44 to an *E. coli* O55:B5 endotoxin challenge ($5 \mu\text{g}/\text{udder half}$) was studied in 9 healthy Lacaune
45 ewes milked once-daily at late-lactation (0.58 ± 0.03 L/d; 155 ± 26 DIM). Ewes were
46 allocated into 3 balanced groups of 3 ewes to which treatments were applied by udder half
47 after milking. Treatments were: 1) control (C00, both udder halves untreated), 2) half udder
48 treated (T10 and C01, one udder half infused with endotoxin and the other untreated,
49 respectively), and 3) treated udder halves (T11, both udder halves infused with endotoxin).
50 Body (vaginal) temperature and UST, milk yield and milk composition changes, were
51 monitored by udder half at different time intervals (2 to 72 h). First local and systemic signs
52 of IMI were observed at 4 and 6-h post-challenge, respectively. For all treatments, UST
53 increased after the challenge, peaking at 6 h in T11 (which differed from C00, C01 and T10),
54 and decreased thereafter without differences by treatment. Vaginal temperature and milk
55 somatic cell count (SCC) increased by 6 h post-challenge, whereas lactose content decreased,

56 in the *E. coli* infused udder halves. Endotoxin effects on lactose and SCC values were
57 detectable in the infused udder halves until 72 h. In conclusion, despite the accuracy of the
58 camera ($\pm 0.15^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the SEM obtained for UST measures (± 0.05 to $\pm 0.24^{\circ}\text{C}$), we were
59 unable to discriminate between healthy and infected (subclinically or clinically) udder halves
60 in dairy ewes.

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62 **Key words:** dairy sheep, infrared thermography, mastitis detection, udder temperature.

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INTRODUCTION

65 Early diagnosis of intramammary infections (**IMI**) is a relevant topic in the dairy industry
66 due to its effects on milk production and treatment related costs. Animals respond to IMI
67 locally (i.e., pain, heat, hardness, swelling) and systemically (i.e., antibody production, body
68 temperature), but the response may vary according to the infectious agent (Rebhun, 1995;
69 McGavin et al., 2007). Thermal response to infection (fever) is a useful indicator in diagnosis
70 which can be observed locally in most IMI cases (Rebhun, 1995).

71 Infrared thermography (**IRT**) is a non-invasive technique which allows the temperature of
72 a surface to be measured without contact. The IRT can generate images of the amount of heat
73 emitted by an object, which has been used to study the changes in udder surface temperature
74 (**UST**) by IMI in dairy cows (Barth, 2000; Scott et al., 2000; Hovinen et al., 2009). Moreover,
75 IRT was able to show changes in teat temperature according to milking parameters in dairy
76 cows (Kunc et al., 2007; Vegricht et al., 2007) and dairy ewes (Murgia et al., 2008). Barth
77 (2000) concluded that IRT showed promise for detecting clinical mastitis, although it was
78 unlikely to be useful for subclinical mastitis detection.

79 Berry et al. (2003) reported daily variations in UST of dairy cows measured by IRT as a
80 consequence of exercise, ambient temperature and circadian rhythm, concluding that UST can

81 be predicted accurately and, the difference between actual and predicted temperature being
82 useful for detecting mastitis. In this sense, Colak et al. (2008) and Polat et al. (2010) indicated
83 that IRT had a predictive diagnostic ability similar to California mastitis test (CMT) in dairy
84 cows. Reported UST changes as a result of the IMI-like process induced by infusing *E. coli*
85 bacteria or endotoxin lipopolysaccharide in dairy cows, varied between 1.0 and 3.0°C (Hovinen
86 et al., 2008; Pezeshki et al., 2011) which fit in the range of the accuracy of most IRT cameras.
87 Nevertheless, Hovinen et al. (2008) stressed that UST changes may be affected by the
88 vasoconstriction of the peripheral blood vessels observed during many IMI episodes.

89 The aim of this study was to evaluate the use of IRT for the measurement of udder surface
90 temperature changes produced by dairy sheep breed and machine milking, and to assess the
91 use of IRT for detecting IMI naturally occurring and induced by *E. coli* endotoxin infusion, at
92 early- or at late-lactation, respectively.

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94

MATERIALS AND METHODS

95 The treatment procedures and animal care conditions were reviewed and approved by the
96 Ethical Committee on Animal and Human Experimentation of the Universitat Autònoma de
97 Barcelona (reference CEEAH 2011/1056).

98

Experiment 1

100

Animal and Management Conditions

102 A total of 83 lactating dairy ewes (Manchega, n = 48; Lacaune, n = 35) from the
103 Experimental Farm of the “Servei de Granges i Camps Experimentals” (SGCE) of the UAB
104 (Bellaterra, Barcelona, Spain), were used after parturition. Ewes were kept in a semi-
105 confinement system, allowed to graze for 6-h daily in an annual Italian ryegrass prairie and

106 supplemented indoors with alfalfa hay ad libitum (1.27 Mcal of NE_L/kg and 20.1% CP; DM
107 basis) and concentrate pellets at a flat rate of 0.8 kg/d (1.75 Mcal NE_L/kg and 16.5% CP; DM
108 basis) distributed in 2 portions at milking times. After the weaning of the lambs (d 35), the
109 ewes were machine milked twice-daily (0800 and 1700 h) in a double-12 stall parallel milking
110 parlor (Amarre Azul I, DeLaval Equipos, Alcobendas, Madrid, Spain) with a central high
111 milk pipeline, 12 DeLaval SG-TF100 milking clusters and 12 MM25SG milk flow and
112 recording units. Milking was performed at a vacuum of 40 kPa, 120 pulses/min and 50%
113 pulsation ratio. The milking routine included cluster attachment (without udder preparation),
114 machine milking and automatic cluster detachment (milk flow rate <0.1 L/min or milking
115 time >3 min). Teat dipping with a iodine solution (P3-ioshield, Ecolab Hispano-Portuguesa,
116 Barcelona, Spain) was done at the end of milking. Teat dipping was done after taking the IRT
117 pictures on the experimental days.

118

119 ***Milk Recording and Sampling***

120 Milk yield of individual ewes was recorded at 60 DIM. Udders and milk were clinically
121 examined for IMI clinical signs (hypersensitivity, hardness, abnormal texture, swelling and
122 hyperthermia) and for physical milk changes (i.e., milk clots, color and consistency changes)
123 according to NMC (1999). Detection of IMI by bacterial culture of foremilk samples were
124 performed by udder half at 15, 34 and 64 DIM.

125 Milk samples were taken out aseptically from each mammary gland before milking. Teats
126 were dipped in a iodine solution (P3-ioshield), dried with disposable paper towels and dipped
127 in ethanol 70% before sampling. The initial milk squirts were discarded and approximately 5
128 mL collected in sterile plastic cap tubes, preserved under refrigeration (4°C) and processed on
129 the same day. Milk samples were cultured using conventional methods and 0.01 mL were
130 streaked onto blood-agar plates (Agar Sangre 90 mm, Lab. Conda, Torrejón de Ardoz,

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131 Madrid) and incubated at 37°C. Plates were examined for bacterial growth after 18, 24 and 48
132 h.

133

134 *Udder Skin Temperature*

135 The UST was measured using a handheld portable infrared imaging camera (IRI 4010,
136 Irisys, Northampton, UK). The camera operated within 8 to 14 μm spectral band and $\pm 0.15^\circ\text{C}$
137 thermal resolution (accuracy). Before each measurement, the camera was adjusted for the
138 ambient temperature conditions of each scanning (9 to 26°C) to compensate the reflected
139 temperature. The emissivity value was set to 0.98 according to the Irisys camera user's
140 manual which is the value commonly used for measuring the skin temperature in humans and
141 in dairy cow's udder (Hovinen et al., 2008).

142 The IRT pictures of each udder were taken immediately before and after milking at 46 and
143 56 DIM. Ewes were restrained in a standing position using the head locker of the milking
144 parlor, and udder pictures were taken from a caudal view placing the camera on a tripod and
145 at 0.5 m distance. Udders were free of debris or fecal materials. Infrared images were
146 downloaded and the UST points analyzed with appropriate computer software (Irisys 4000
147 Series Imager v.1.0.0.17). Representative UST values of each udder half were obtained from
148 the full udder IRT images (640 \times 480 pixels) by selecting a rectangle of 55 \times 40 pixels in the
149 centre of the cisternal part of each udder half (Figure 1). Special care was taken to avoid the
150 influence of heat from the groin, the leg and the median suspensory ligament as they showed
151 higher temperatures than the rest of the udder. Mean UST for each udder half was obtained
152 using a 4 \times zoom by averaging the temperatures recorded in the centre of each side of the
153 selected rectangle.

154 Skin thickness of the udder was measured after p.m. milking in duplicate in a random
155 sample of 10 ewes of each breed with healthy udders. With this aim, the width of a fold of

156 udder skin in 2 positions at the middle line of the udder perineal region (escutcheon) were
157 measured at the end of the experiment and approximately 4 h after milking using a stainless
158 steel electronic digital calliper (Yicheng, Beijing, China).

159

160 ***Experiment 2***

161

162 ***Animal and Management Conditions***

163 Nine healthy primiparous Lacaune dairy ewes (60.2 ± 0.8 kg BW) at the end of lactation
164 (155 ± 26 DIM and 0.58 ± 0.03 L/d) from the Experimental Farm of the SGCE were used.
165 Ewes were maintained indoors in straw bedded pens ($1 \text{ m}^2/\text{ewe}$) and fed a mix of alfalfa and
166 tall fescue hays (2:1) ad libitum and the same concentrate mixture (0.6 kg/d, as fed) used in
167 Exp.1. Once-daily milking was conducted (0800 h) in a 12-stall milking parlor (Westfalia-
168 Surge Ibérica, Granollers, Spain) equipped with recording jars ($2 \text{ L} \pm 5\%$) and a low milk
169 pipeline. Milking was performed at a vacuum of 42 kPa, 120 pulses/min, and a 50% pulsation
170 ratio. The milking routine included cluster attachment, machine milking, machine stripping
171 before cluster removal, and teat dipping in a iodine solution (P3-ioshield).

172 No signs of IMI were detected in any udder half either by clinical examination or CMT
173 (Insvet, Esplus, Huesca, Spain) of foremilk before the experiment. Absence of intramammary
174 infections was also confirmed by bacterial culture as done in Exp. 1.

175 Ewes were assigned to 3 balanced groups of 3 ewes to which the experimental treatments
176 were randomly applied.

177

178 ***Endotoxin Challenge***

179 Treatments consisted of intramammary challenges of *Escherichia coli* serotype O55:B5
180 endotoxin lipopolysaccharide (Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis, MO) for inducing an intramammary

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181 response similar to a mastitis-like process, and were: 1) control (**C00**, both udder halves
182 untreated; n = 3 ewes), 2) half udder treated (**T10** and **C01**, one udder half was endotoxin
183 infused and the other half was untreated, respectively; n = 3 ewes), and 3) both udder halves
184 treated (**T11**, both udder halves were endotoxin infused; n = 3 ewes).

185 A solution of 5 µg/mL *E. coli* O55:B5 endotoxin in physiological saline (NaCl-0.9%; B
186 Braun, Barcelona, Spain) was aseptically prepared and preserved in 1 mL sterilized vials
187 under refrigeration (4°C). The endotoxin challenge consisted of infusing 1 mL endotoxin
188 solution (5 µg/udder half) through the teat canal of the T10 (half udder) and T11 (both udder
189 halves) ewe udders by using individual aseptic plastic cannulas (Mod. J-2, length 1½",
190 Jorgensen Laboratories, Loveland, CO) cut to 18 mm long and with 2.5 mm outside diameter
191 at approximately 30 min after the morning milking.

192

193 *Clinical Observations and Milk Sampling*

194 The experimental period lasted for 3 d in which the clinical and productive stages of the
195 udder halves were monitored after the challenge. Systemic (body temperature and udder
196 appearance) and local (redness, hardness and UST) signs of reaction to the endotoxin
197 challenge were monitored at 1 h, every 2-h (2 to 12 h), every 12-h (12 to 72 h), and
198 additionally at 25, 28, 32, 49 and 73 h post-challenge.

199 Body temperature (systemic sign of reaction) was measured vaginally at the above indicated
200 hours using a clinical thermometer (Model mini color, ICO Technology, Barcelona, Spain;
201 range, 32.0 to 43.9°C; accuracy, ± 0.1°C). Udders and milk were also subjected to physical
202 examination for IMI according to Exp.1 procedures.

203 Milk yield was recorded and milk samples collected (for CMT, milk composition and SCC)
204 by udder half during the pre-experimental week and, at each milking throughout the
205 experiment (d 1 to 3). Additional milk samples were collected manually at 6, 24, 48 and 72 h

206 post-challenge. For milk composition and SCC analyses, samples of approximately 50 mL
207 were preserved with anti-microbial tablets (Bronopol, Broad Spectrum Micro-tabs II, D&F
208 Control Systems Inc., San Ramon, CA) and kept at 4°C until processing. Both milk
209 composition and SCC were determined in the interprofessional dairy laboratory of Catalonia
210 (Allic, Cabrils, Barcelona, Spain), using an automatic somatic cell counter (Fossomatic 500,
211 Foss-Electric, Hillerød, Denmark) previously calibrated for ewes milk.

212

213 *Udder Skin Temperature*

214 The UST was measured using the procedure described in Exp.1, taken a total of 17 IRT
215 images from each ewe's udder immediately before and at different times after the challenge
216 (same as for body temperatures). Images were obtained from the untouched udders, before
217 udder examination and milk sampling to avoid stress induced hyperthermia (Bouwknicht et
218 al., 2007).

219

220 *Statistical Analyses*

221 Data of both experiments were analyzed using the PROC MIXED of SAS v.9.1 (SAS Inst.
222 Inc., Cary, NC) and variation factors compared by classes. The mixed model used for Exp.1
223 data contained the fixed effects of udder health (healthy and IMI), breed (Manchega and
224 Lacaune), milking moment (before and after) and milking schedule (a.m. and p.m.), and the
225 random effects of the ewe (1 to 83) and the error.

226 Model used in Exp. 2 contained the fixed effects of treatment (C00, T11, C01 and T10),
227 time post-challenge (0 to 73 h), and the random effects of the ewe (1 to 9) and the error.

228 Performance data before the endotoxin challenge were used as a covariate to correct for
229 individual initial differences and results were presented as least squares means. Differences
230 between least squares means were determined with the PDIFF option of SAS. Logarithmic

231 transformations (\log_{10}) of SCC values were used in the statistical analysis. Pearson's
232 correlations were used to determine the relationship between the studied variables.
233 Significance was declared as $P < 0.05$, unless otherwise indicated, and tendencies were
234 discussed at $P < 0.10$.

235

236

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

237

238 *Experiment 1*

239

240 *Milk Yield*

241 Experimental ewes yielded 1.46 ± 0.04 L/d, on average, at 60 DIM. When classified
242 according to the bacterial culture, subclinical IMI ewes yielded 12% less milk than the
243 healthy ones, although the difference was not significant (1.37 ± 0.08 vs. 1.49 ± 0.06 L/d; $P =$
244 0.212). A lower milk yield was expected in the IMI ewes according to different authors
245 (Viguier et al., 2009; Pezeshki et al., 2011), although the difference with the healthy ewes
246 may have been reduced as a result of the low incidence of udder halves suffering subclinical
247 mastitis (12.1%) and the compensatory milk yield of the contralateral udder half (Leitner et
248 al., 2004).

249

250 *Subclinical Mastitis*

251 From the 166 udder halves utilized, a total of 20 (12.0%) were classified as IMI by bacterial
252 culture in at least 2 of the 3 tests made at 15, 34 and 64 DIM. The subclinical IMI ewes did
253 not present signs of mastitis and their milk was apparently normal but showed high SCC
254 ($>300 \times 10^3$ cells/mL, according to McDougall et al., 2001). Reported values of incidence of
255 subclinical mastitis in dairy cows are also markedly greater than in ewes (Lam et al., 2013; 22
256 to 23%).

257 No differences in UST values were detected between healthy and subclinical IMI udders of
258 the same ewes throughout the experiment, but the IMI udders tended to show slightly lower
259 mean UST values than the healthy udders (33.13 vs. 33.61°C, respectively; SEM = ±0.28; $P =$
260 0.095). These results are contrary to those of Martins et al. (2013) who reported greater UST
261 values in subclinical mastitis than in healthy udders of Santa Inês ewes (37.46 vs. 37.05°C,
262 respectively), although the number of ewes (healthy, 16; subclinical mastitis, 8), size of the
263 udder (meat sheep) and the cleaning process (using warm water) may have conditioned the
264 results. Moreover, no differences were reported by Martins et al. (2013) for total udder mean
265 temperatures (36.30 vs. 36.06°C, respectively).

266

267 *Clinical Mastitis*

268 A total of 4 udder halves (3 ewes, 3.6%) showed clinical mastitis and required antibiotic
269 treatment. These IMI udders showed local and systemic mastitis clinical signs (severe
270 swelling, tissue hardness and redness) and marked changes in milk appearance (flakes, watery
271 and abnormal texture). Prevalence of clinical mastitis is generally not greater than 5% in dairy
272 sheep (Berger et al., 2004) as observed in our data. Incidence of clinical mastitis is markedly
273 greater in dairy cows when compared to dairy sheep, ranging between 28 and 33.5% quarter
274 cases as reported in Canada (Olde Riekerink et al., 2008) and the Netherlands (Lam et al.,
275 2013).

276 Mean UST values for clinical IMI varied largely and, on average, were slightly greater than
277 for the healthy udder halves although they did not differ (33.51 vs. 33.47°C, respectively;
278 SEM = ±1.13; $P = 0.972$). Infrared thermography images of the only ewe presenting a clinical
279 IMI in both udder halves compared with a fully healthy udder are shown in Figure 1. High
280 temperature pixels are shown by lighter grey. Martins et al. (2013) reported lower UST values
281 but no differences between clinical mastitis and healthy udders (36.67 vs. 37.05°C; $n = 13$)

282 which was considered as a response to the decreased blood flow which was a consequence of
 283 the mammary gland loss of function. Moreover, Hovinen et al. (2008) indicated that UST
 284 changes may be affected by the vasoconstriction of the peripheral blood vessels observed
 285 during IMI episodes, producing a decrease in skin temperature.

286

287 *Udder Temperature Variation Factors*

288 Table 1 summarizes the effects of the main factors considered in the study to explain the
 289 variation of UST values in the experimental ewes. Overall mean UST ($32.94 \pm 0.04^{\circ}\text{C}$) was
 290 lower than the average body temperature reported for sheep (38.0 to 39.5°C ; Adams and
 291 McKinley, 2009) and it was affected by most of the studied factors (i.e., breed, milking
 292 schedule and milking moment; $P < 0.05$ to 0.001). Values of UST were lower in the
 293 Manchega compared to the Lacaune breed ewes ($P < 0.01$; Table 1), which agrees with their
 294 lower milk yield observed in our data for the healthy ewes (1.25 vs. 1.72 L/d; $\text{SEM} = \pm 0.97$;
 295 $P < 0.001$). No previous data on the relationship of milk yield and UST has been reported.
 296 Moreover, no differences in udder skin fold thickness were detected between Manchega and
 297 Lacaune ewes (15.82 ± 0.13 vs. 15.79 ± 0.07 mm, respectively; $P = 0.896$) but we noted that
 298 Manchega ewes had more frequently the presence of hair in their udders than Lacaune.
 299 According to Mitchell (2013), hair presence may have decreased the UST values and
 300 contributed to the breed differences above indicated.

301 The UST values before milking were lower at the morning milking than at the afternoon
 302 milking ($P < 0.001$; Table 1), which may be related with the circadian rhythm of body
 303 temperatures, exercise and feeding behavior (Berry et al., 2003; Piccione and Caola, 2003;
 304 D'Alterio et al., 2011). Moreover, UST correlated with ambient temperature ($y = 0.37 x +$
 305 28.4 ; $r = 0.88$; $P < 0.001$). Indoor ambient temperature was $12.18 \pm 0.74^{\circ}\text{C}$ on average,
 306 ranging between 9.1 and 16.6°C during the experiment. Loughmiller et al. (2001) also

307 reported a correlation ($r = 0.98$) between ambient temperature (10 to 32°C) and body surface
308 temperature measured by IRT in pigs; each 1°C increment caused an increase of 0.40°C in the
309 body surface temperature of pigs.

310 Additionally, UST values increased by effect of milking ($P < 0.05$; Table 1), which agreed
311 with the conclusions of Kunc et al. (2007) and was attributed to the hyperemia by udder
312 manipulation. Figure 2 shows the IRT images of the udder of the same ewe before and after
313 milking. Nevertheless, Murgia et al. (2008) in sheep and Aljumaah et al. (2012) in camels
314 reported a decrease in the temperature of the teats and the udder, measured by IRT, as a
315 consequence of machine milking. Differences in the UST response to machine milking may
316 also be due to the operating vacuum and milk yield (Kunc et al., 2007). Vegricht et al. (2007)
317 reported lower increments in UST in dairy cows by lower milking vacuums.

318 No effects were detected in our ewes in udder side and udder health status ($P > 0.05$; Table
319 1), allowing us to use pooled data and agreeing with the IMI data above discussed.

320

321 ***Experiment 2***

322 ***Clinical Signs and Body Temperature***

323 Local and systemic signs of IMI in the T10 and T11 mammary glands were clearly
324 observed after endotoxin infusion despite the dose used by udder half (0.083 µg/kg BW).
325 None of the ewes had a severe reaction to the endotoxin challenge. The T10 and T11 ewes
326 were calm after endotoxin infusion and did not present signs of pain or hypersensitivity,
327 although 2 ewes of each treatment showed udders with moderate swelling and tissue hardness
328 approximately 4 h after infusion. Clinical signs were similar to those observed in an acute
329 IMI.

330 Body temperature, measured by vaginal temperature of the T10 and T11 ewes increased
331 after endotoxin infusion (Figure 3), peaking at 4 to 6 h after the challenge. In parallel, vaginal

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332 temperature of C00 ewes slowly increased after milking likely ambient temperature and
333 peaked 6 h after milking. Positive correlations of the vaginal temperature (x) with ambient
334 temperature (y) were detected for the healthy ewes ($y = 4.426x - 141.88$; $r = 0.55$; $P < 0.001$),
335 indicating that the observed increased temperature was unlikely due to the IMI response and
336 could be a consequence of the rise in ambient temperature, agreeing with data of Exp. 1.
337 Vickers et al. (2010) validated the use of vaginal loggers to measure body temperature which
338 has the advantage of not being affected by the presence of feces. Willard et al. (2007) also
339 reported increased body temperatures after an endotoxin in dairy cows, but the authors did not
340 correlate this with the increased ambient temperature also recorded in the experiment.

341 The endotoxin dose used in our experiment was low compared to those used in dairy
342 cows, which ranged between 0.02 and 2.60 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ BW of *E. coli* O55:B5 (Hovinen et al.,
343 2008; Willard et al., 2007; respectively), but was enough to induce dramatic changes in milk
344 appearance (milk flakes and yellow color) 6 h after the challenge; the 3 T11 ewes showing
345 abundant flakes in their milk. A higher dose was used by Scott et al. (2000) in dairy cows but
346 no information is available on the *E. coli* serotype used. Udder swelling disappeared gradually
347 and was hardly detectable 24 h after the challenge as reported in dairy cows (Scott et al.,
348 2000).

349

350 ***Milk Yield and Composition***

351 Regarding milk production, all groups of ewes decreased milk yield on the day of
352 treatment, which may have been a consequence of the experimental management and isolation
353 of the ewes from the flock on the day before (Sufka and Hughes, 1991). Nevertheless, in
354 agreement with the IMI signs of the T10 and T11 infused ewes, a greater milk yield drop was
355 observed in the endotoxin treated udder halves after infusion (Figure 4). On average, daily
356 milk yield drop in the treated (T10 and T11) vs. the untreated (C00 and C01) udder halves at

357 24, 48 and 72 h post-challenge, were -33.1 ($P < 0.05$), -41.4 ($P < 0.001$) and -36.6% ($P <$
358 0.001) respectively, when compared to 0 h. All ewes increased milk yield at 48 h except the
359 T10 ewes which steadied but recovered at 72 h. As a consequence C00 and C01 ewe groups
360 recovered their initial milk yield before the challenge, while the T10 and T11 showed an
361 incomplete recuperation after 72 h. Lehtolainen et al. (2003) reported a complete recovery of
362 the udder of dairy cows on d 2 after the challenge, which was not observed in our results and
363 may be a consequence of the involution stage of the mammary gland induced by the once-a-
364 day milking at the end of lactation (Boutinaud et al., 2003).

365 Changes in milk components as a result of the endotoxin challenge varied according to the
366 milk component considered (Table 2), being moderate in fat, protein and total solids and
367 dramatic in lactose and SCC. The effect of endotoxin challenge on fat, protein and total solids
368 contents were only significant 6 h after the challenge and no effects were detected in their
369 corresponding daily milk yields, except in the total solid yield at 72 h which was showing the
370 first signs of recovery (Table 2; $P > 0.05$). Lactose content dramatically decreased in the T01
371 and T11 groups 6-h after the challenge ($P < 0.001$), showing a nadir at 24-h and signs of
372 recovery at 72-h, when compared to the control groups (Table 2). Similar effects were
373 detected in lactose daily yield ($P < 0.05$). A decrease in lactose output was also reported by
374 Leitner et al. (2004) in subclinical mastitis milk of dairy ewes, which was attributed to the
375 local role of casein hydrolyzed peptides on the activity of mammary epithelial cells
376 (Silanikove et al., 2000). Martins et al. (2013) also reported lower lactose levels in the milk of
377 ewes with clinical mastitis, supporting the theory that the secretory tissue damage leads to a
378 decrease in lactose biosyntheses. On the other hand, \log_{10} SCC increased in the milk of the
379 endotoxin treated groups (13 to 26%, $P < 0.005$; Table 1) and stayed high during the
380 experiment (Lehtolainen et al., 2003), the effect being consistent 72 h after the endotoxin
381 challenge and with the decrease in milk lactose contents. These results confirm the adequacy

382 of the endotoxin dose used in our ewes and the persistency of the mastitis clinical signs above
 383 discussed, agreeing with those reported by Hovinen et al. (2008) in dairy cows treated with a
 384 low dose of endotoxin.

385

386 *Udder Skin Temperature*

387 Dramatic changes in the UST values were shown throughout the experimental period
 388 (Figure 5) which peaked 2 to 6 h after milking. Indoor ambient temperature, also shown in the
 389 same figure, was $23.00 \pm 0.38^{\circ}\text{C}$ on average, ranging between 20.6 and 26.6°C during the
 390 experiment, peaking at 36 h and slowly declining thereafter.

391 A circadian rhythm pattern was observed daily for UST, with minimum and maximum
 392 values before and after milking, respectively (Figure 5). This pattern indicated the influence
 393 of the variation in the daily temperature and management conditions. Nevertheless, no
 394 differences between treatments were observed for the mean UST values during the
 395 experiment ($P = 0.752$), with the exception of T11 which showed a peak at h 6 after the
 396 challenge ($P < 0.001$).

397 The lack of differences in the UST mean values by effect of the treatments agreed with the
 398 fact that UST values largely vary between udder halves of the same animal despite the
 399 treatment applied. Range of differences between udder halves of the same animal were high
 400 for C00 (0.05 to 0.55°C) and T10 (0.05 to 0.85°C) and increased in the case of T11 (0.10 to
 401 1.00°C), indicating a large local variation in the UST values of healthy halves and in the
 402 response to the infection in the endotoxin infused udder halves. These differences in the
 403 response to the endotoxin challenge between udder halves have not been reported previously.
 404 Our results agreed with those of Scott et al. (2000), Hovinen et al. (2008) and Pezeshki et al.
 405 (2011), which showed a similar increase of UST in the experimental and controls halves,
 406 reflecting the systemic effect of the infused endotoxin. Moreover, positive correlations

407 between vaginal and ambient temperature (above indicated), between UST (x) and vaginal (y)
408 temperatures ($y = 0.182x + 31.92$; $r = 0.69$; $P < 0.001$) and between ambient (x) and UST
409 temperatures ($y = 0.508x + 25.42$; $r = 0.62$; $P < 0.001$) in our data also supported the lack of
410 effects of the experimental treatments.

411 Barth (2000) and Polat et al. (2010) reported significant UST differences (+0.5 and
412 +2.35°C, respectively) in dairy cows between udder quarters with SCC below and above 100
413 and 400×10^3 cells/mL, respectively. Polat et al. (2010) also found a medium and positive
414 correlation between UST and SCC ($r = 0.73$) which was lower in our ewe data ($r = 0.25$; $P =$
415 0.032). Additionally, Colak et al. (2008) and Polat et al. (2010) found positive correlations
416 between UST and CMT values by udder in dairy cows ($r = 0.92$ and $r = 0.86$, respectively),
417 but the correlation of UST with CMT was lower and not significant in our data ($r = 0.18$; $P =$
418 0.503). These results did not allow us to discriminate between the UST values of endotoxin
419 infused and healthy udder halves in our data, the variation observed being attributed to
420 individual and environmental differences.

421 Our results disagree with those of Polat et al. (2010) who found 83.5% sensitivity and
422 100% specificity for a cut-off of 34.7°C when udder quarters were classified as healthy or
423 infected with subclinical mastitis ($>200 \times 10^3$ cells/mL). Previous research showed that
424 commercial thermal cameras are capable of detecting 1.0 to 3.0°C temperature changes of
425 udder surface in cows intramammary infused with *E. coli* endotoxin (Hovinen et al., 2008;
426 Pezeshki et al., 2011). In our results the thermal camera was able to detect the 1 to 1.3°C
427 changes in UST associated with the *E. coli* endotoxin challenge in ewes.

428

429

CONCLUSIONS

430 Thermal imaging was a simple and fast, noninvasive technique to measure the skin
431 temperature of the mammary gland in dairy ewes at milking. Nevertheless, despite the

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432 resolution of the camera used ($\pm 0.15^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the SEM obtained for UST measures (± 0.05 to
433 $\pm 0.24^{\circ}\text{C}$), we were unable to discriminate between healthy, infected (subclinical or clinical)
434 or infused with a *E. coli* lipopolysaccharide endotoxin udder halves in dairy ewes. Other
435 factors (breed, ambient temperature, milking) can induce changes in UST greater than those
436 observed after clinical or subclinical IMI.

437

438

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443

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540

541 **Table 1.** Effect of the experimental variation factors on the udder skin temperatures (UST, °C)
542 of dairy ewes

Factor ¹	Class 1	Class 2	SEM	Effect (<i>P</i> =)
Breed	32.88	33.23	0.11	0.003
Milking schedule	32.66	33.45	0.06	0.001
Milking moment	32.99	33.12	0.05	0.014
Side of the udder	33.05	33.06	0.11	0.879
Health status of udder	33.11	33.00	0.16	0.484

543 ¹Factor classes: Breed (class 1, Manchega; class 2, Lacaune), milking schedule (class 1, a.m.; class 2,
544 p.m.), milking moment (class 1, before; class 2, after), side of the udder (class 1, left, class 2, right)
545 and health status of udder (class 1, healthy; class 2, subclinical IMI).

546

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547 **Table 2.** Effect of the *E. coli* lipopolysaccharide (LPS) infusion treatments on milk composition by udder half of
548 dairy ewes at the end of lactation

Item	Time ² , h	Treatment ¹				SEM	Treatment effect (P =)
		Control		LPS infused			
		C00	C01	T10	T11		
Fat, %	6	9.82 ^{ab}	9.33 ^b	7.96 ^a	8.26 ^{ab}	0.34	0.084
	24	7.22	7.42	8.19	8.23	0.48	0.761
	48	6.46	5.40	9.54	7.56	0.57	0.173
	72	6.38	5.99	7.05	6.91	0.47	0.805
Fat yield, g/d	6	—	—	—	—	—	—
	24	22	21	17	18	2	0.619
	48	25	22	16	21	3	0.652
	72	24	29	23	20	2	0.117
Protein, %	6	6.04 ^b	5.80 ^{ab}	5.60 ^{ab}	5.55 ^a	0.06	0.044
	24	6.07	5.94	7.33	6.80	0.19	0.102
	48	6.03	6.02	7.89	6.60	0.23	0.154
	72	6.44	6.17	6.48	6.09	0.10	0.352
Protein yield, g/d	6	—	—	—	—	—	—
	24	20	17	14	14	2	0.500
	48	25	23	14	18	2	0.204
	72	26	31	24	18	2	0.053
Lactose, %	6	4.46 ^c	4.51 ^c	2.73 ^a	3.47 ^b	0.12	0.001
	24	4.29 ^c	4.48 ^c	2.02 ^a	2.92 ^b	0.10	0.003
	48	4.13 ^c	4.42 ^c	2.90 ^a	3.11 ^a	0.13	0.003
	72	4.12 ^{ab}	4.23 ^{bc}	3.59 ^a	3.73 ^{ac}	0.13	0.002
Lactose yield, g/d	6	—	—	—	—	—	—
	24	14	13	5	7	1	0.020
	48	17	17	6	8	1	0.040
	72	18	21	12	10	1	0.003
Total solids, %	6	21.5 ^{bc}	20.6 ^c	17.5 ^{ab}	18.1 ^a	0.4	0.006
	24	18.6	19.0	19.1	19.1	0.6	0.988
	48	17.4	17.1	23.5	18.6	0.8	0.187
	72	18.3	17.2	16.7	17.1	0.4	0.667
Solids yield, g/d	6	—	—	—	—	—	—
	24	59	54	39	42	5	0.293
	48	73	67	37	52	6	0.194
	72	71 ^{bc}	84 ^c	62 ^{ab}	50 ^a	5	0.001
Log ₁₀ SCC	6	5.66 ^a	5.88 ^a	7.22 ^b	7.27 ^b	0.06	0.001
	24	5.46 ^a	5.91 ^a	6.24 ^a	7.32 ^b	0.17	0.005
	48	5.32 ^a	5.49 ^a	7.28 ^b	7.13 ^b	0.05	0.001
	72	5.24 ^a	5.27 ^a	6.37 ^b	6.69 ^b	0.07	0.001

549 ^{a-c}Means within a row with different superscripts differ ($P < 0.05$).

550 ¹Treatments by udder half were: both udder halves untreated (C00, control); half udder treated (T10 and C01,
551 one udder half was LPS infused and the other half was untreated, respectively); and, both udder halves treated
552 (T11, both udder halves were LPS infused).

553 ²Time after the LPS challenge.

554

555 **FIGURE CAPTIONS**

556 **Figure 1.** Infrared thermographic images of clinically intramammary infected udder halves
557 (left) and healthy udder halves (right) of dairy ewes done in the milking parlor for an indoor
558 ambient temperature ranging between 9.1 and 16.6°C. Thermal histogram of the full image is
559 shown under each image and udder skin temperature extreme values shown in brackets. Dotted
560 rectangles on each udder half are the selected frame of 55 × 40 pixels in which the skin
561 temperature was measured.

562

563 **Figure 2.** Infrared thermographic images of healthy udders of dairy ewes before (left) and
564 after (right) milking done in the milking parlor for an indoor ambient temperature ranging
565 between 9.1 and 16.6°C. Thermal histogram is shown under each image and udder skin
566 temperature extreme values shown in brackets. Note the presence of a supernumerary teat in
567 the left udder half.

568

569 **Figure 3.** Changes in vaginal temperature of dairy ewes submitted to an *E. coli* endotoxin
570 lipopolysaccharide challenge at late-lactation. Treatments by udder half were: both udder
571 halves untreated (○, C00, control), half udder treated (▲, T10 and C01, one udder half was
572 LPS infused and the other half was untreated, respectively), and both udder halves treated (●,
573 T11, both udder halves were endotoxin infused). Experimental details: *E. coli* challenge (⬆),
574 once-daily milking (⬇) and ambient temperature in the barn (---). Values are means with
575 SEM indicated by vertical bars.

576

577 **Figure 4.** Effect of the infusion of *E. coli* endotoxin lipopolysaccharide (LPS) on the milk
578 yield of dairy ewes at late-lactation by half udder (○, untreated; ●, LPS infused). Treatments:
579 both udder halves untreated (---, C00, control), half udders treated (---, C01, untreated
580 udder half; - • -, T10, treated udder half) and both udder halves treated (- •• -, T11, both
581 udder halves infused). Experimental details: *E. coli* challenge (⬆) and once-daily milking
582 (⬇). Values are least squares means with SEM indicated by vertical bars.

583

584 **Figure 5.** Changes in udder skin temperature of dairy ewes submitted to an *E. coli* endotoxin
585 lipopolysaccharide (LPS) challenge at late-lactation. Treatments by udder half were: both
586 udder halves untreated (○, C00, control), half udder treated (▲, T10 and C01, one udder half

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587 was LPS infused and the other half was untreated, respectively), and both udder halves treated
588 (●, T11, both udder halves were endotoxin infused). Experimental details: *E. coli* challenge
589 (▲), once-daily milking (▼) and ambient temperature in the barn (---). Values are means
590 with SEM indicated by vertical bars.

591 **Figure 1.** *by Castro-Costa*

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594 **Figure 2.** *by Castro-Costa*

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596 **Figure 3.** *by Castro-Costa*

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599 **Figure 4.** by Castro-Costa.

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601 **Figure 5.** by Castro-Costa.

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